
Deliverable JIP1-1.3

Revised OH Surveillance Codex, including lessons learned from the OH pilots

Workpackage 1

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GENERAL INFORMATION

European Joint Programme full title	Promoting One Health in Europe through joint actions on foodborne zoonoses, antimicrobial resistance and emerging microbiological hazards
European Joint Programme acronym	One Health EJP
Funding	This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 773830.
Grant Agreement	Grant agreement n° 773830
Start Date	01/01/2018
Duration	60 Months

DOCUMENT MANAGEMENT

Deliverable	JIP1-1.3 Revised OH Surveillance Codex, including lessons learned from the OH pilots
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Due month of the deliverable	M42
Actual submission month	M42
Type <i>R: Document, report</i> <i>DEC: Websites, patent filings, videos, etc.</i> <i>OTHER</i>	R
Dissemination level <i>PU: Public</i> <i>CO: confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)</i>	PU

REVISED ONE HEALTH SURVEILLANCE CODEX, INCLUDING LESSONS LEARNED FROM THE PILOTS

1. Background

The ORION project aimed at the prototypic implementation of an integrated strategy to establish and strengthen the inter-institutional collaboration and transdisciplinary knowledge transfer in the area of One Health Surveillance (OHS) data integration and interpretation. This strategy was initially called ORION “OHS harmonization framework” and consisted of three pillars:

- An “OHS Codex” (ORION WP1) - a high level framework for harmonised, cross-sectional description and categorisation of surveillance data covering all surveillance phases and all knowledge types.
- An “OHS Knowledge Hub” (ORION WP2) - a cross-domain inventory of public/veterinary health data sources as well as algorithms and tools supporting OHS data generation, integration, analysis and interpretation.
- “OHS Infrastructure Resources” (ORION WP3) – technical and infrastructural resources that form the basis for successful harmonization and integration of surveillance data and methods.

2. The initial concept of the OHS Codex

The OHS Codex aimed by WP1 had the primary focus of providing descriptive guidelines that support the categorization of cross-sectoral OHS metadata and the mutual understanding between and within different OHS domains. For the development of these guidelines a requirement analysis was carried out during the first year of the project (described in deliverable [D-JIP1-D1.1¹](#)). This analysis included literature reviews, online surveys and individual interviews with experts from the animal, food and public health sectors. As a result of this analysis, it was outlined the lack of resources supporting mutual understanding and interpretation of data from the different OHS domains, which is a major bottleneck for meaningful OHS data analysis. In order to facilitate and contribute to mutual understanding between OH sectors, it was decided that the WP1 should work of two different solutions:

- a guidance document for harmonized categorization of metadata from different OHS domains providing recommendations on how to structure metadata in future surveillance data reports.
- a community driven glossary collecting One Health (OH) related terms that helps to identify terms with different or shared interpretation across sectors helping to overcome communication hurdles in the future

¹ ORION. (2020, April 16). Deliverable-JIP1-D1.1 Report on requirement analysis for OH Surveillance Codex (ORION). Zenodo. <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3754468>

3. Conceptual re-design phase

In the second year of the project, the outcomes from the requirement analysis phase collected by the different ORION WPs were brought together during the prioritization workshop (details provided in the ORION 12 Month Report for Year 2). The collected feedback confirmed that cross-sectoral and multi-disciplinary communication, collaboration, dissemination, data interoperability and knowledge exchange are still significant challenges for true OH surveillance activities. During this event, ORION partners synchronized their research and development work taking important organizational decisions. Within WP1, this involved a new conceptual design for both the originally planned OHS Codex and the OHS harmonization framework:

- Regarding the original OHS Codex concept, it was agreed that this guidance document should be provided as a checklist that helps to provide best practice annotation of surveillance data in reports from different OH sectors. This led to the decision to rename the original “OHS Codex” to “OH Consensus Report Annotation Checklist (OH-CRAC)”.
- Regarding the originally used term “OHS harmonization framework”, it was decided to give that concept the name OHS Codex instead. Thus, the term “OHS Codex” evolved into a framework that serves as an umbrella for all resources supporting the adoption of the OH paradigm in the surveillance data generation process. It also allows provipractical examples and lessons learned from pilot studies carried out in the ORION project.

4. OHS Codex

The OHS Codex aims at establishing a high-level framework that supports mutual understanding and information exchange between OHS sectors, which are requisites for integrated OHS data analyses. To bring this framework into “action” the OHS Codex postulates a set of four high-level principles that respectively support: collaboration, knowledge exchange, data interoperability and dissemination. Within each of these principles, the OHS Codex provides a collection of resources (e.g. tools, technical solutions, guidance documents) and examples/lessons learned from the implementation of these resources (see Figure 1). The design of the OHS Codex follows the ambitions and supports the practical implementation of the actions proposed by the “Tripartite Guide to Addressing Zoonotic Diseases in Countries”², which highlights the importance of multi-sectorial OHS information sharing.

The OHS Codex and the solutions described in there are envisioned as a “living” framework and therefore, it undergoes regular reviews and updates as the project and the developed resources evolve. Currently the OHS Codex contains solutions that were developed within the ORION project, but the framework is designed in a way that resources from other EJP projects can easily and continuously be integrated. A collaboration plan has already been established with the EJP MATRIX project to further extend and maintain the OHS Codex once the ORION project ends. The OHS Codex also contains “lessons learned”, summaries from the pilot studies that have been performed to improve OHS data integration and interpretation on the national or international level. From a technical perspective the OHS Codex is implemented as an open source community resource that is available via: <https://oh-surveillance->

² WHO, FAO, & OIE. (2019). *Taking a Multisectoral, One Health Approach: A Tripartite Guide to Addressing Zoonotic Diseases in Countries* Retrieved from <http://www.fao.org/3/ca2942en/ca2942en.pdf>

codex.readthedocs.io/en/latest/index.html.

Figure 1. The conceptual design of the OHS Codex, postulating four high-level principles together with practical tools/technical solutions for improved OHS information sharing.

In order to disseminate the OHS Codex research work, a manuscript describing the OHS-Codex, its design and structure was submitted to the OH journal³. The paper also contains the application examples of the different resources developed under each principle.

5. One Health Consensus Report Annotation Checklist (OH-CRAC)

OH-CRAC provides guidance to researchers and reporting officers from any OH-related sector on what meta-information should be provided to improve the completeness and transparency of data provided in surveillance data reports. The checklist supports the mapping of surveillance meta-information from sector-specific surveillance data reports on federal, national and international level and can be adopted by all OH-related sectors. Based on the requirement analysis results, it was decided that OH-CRAC should build on the Generic Statistical Business Process Model (GSBPM) (<https://statswiki.unece.org/display/GSBPM/GSBPM+v5.1>⁴). GSBPM is a framework established by UNECE (United Nations Economic Commission for Europe), Eurostat (Statistical office of the European Union) and OECD (Organisation for Economic Co-operation

³ Filter, M., Buschhardt, T., Dórea, F., Lopez de Abechucó, E., Günther, T., Sundermann, E. M., . . . Ellis-Iversen, J. (2021). One Health Surveillance Codex: promoting the adoption of One Health solutions within and across European countries. *One Health*, 12, 100233. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.onehlt.2021.100233>

⁴ UNECE. (2019). Generic Statistical Business Process Model GSBPM (Version 5.1, January 2019). Retrieved from <https://statswiki.unece.org/display/GSBPM/GSBPM+v5.1>

and Development). This model is used by official statistical institutions to structure their international and interdisciplinary data provisioning and metadata harmonization activities. In order to apply the GSBPM in a surveillance data annotation context, we aligned the GSBPM structure to the OH Surveillance Pathway⁵ developed within the ORION project (Figure 2A). As a result of this alignment, we could identify the phases and tasks within surveillance activities from different OH sectors and adapt the GSBPM schema to our purpose simplifying it to 5 operational phases: “Specify needs”, “Design”, “Collect”, “Process” and “Analyse”. In this process the terminology and descriptions of the remaining phases were adapted to the OHS context and examples of possible metadata entries were provided to support the checklist users (Figure 2B).

⁵ <https://oh-surveillance-codex.readthedocs.io/en/latest/2-the-collaboration-principle.html?highlight=pathway#oh-surveillance-pathway-visualization>

Figure 2. Overview of the OH-CRAC development process (A-C) and (D) the resulting OH-CRAC annotation sections and their corresponding meta-information items.

To support a broad adoption of this framework by stakeholders from OH-related sectors, OH-CRAC was mapped to existing domain-specific annotation frameworks to validate its cross-domain applicability and identify missing meta-information items that are used by existing domain-specific best practices (Figure 2C). The resulting OH-CRAC is structured in five main reporting sections (specify needs, design, collect, process and analyse) outlined together with their corresponding reporting subheadings in Figure 2D.

Moreover, OH-CRAC was also made available as an interactive online tool (<https://aflex.vrac.iastate.edu/checklist/?t=OH-CRAC>⁶) that allows the provisioning of surveillance meta-information in an easy and user-friendly manner. This tool generates for the user the completed OH-CRAC checklist based on selected text snippets from a user-provided document. Completed OH-CRAC checklists can then be attached as appendices to the corresponding surveillance data reports or even to individual data files. In this way, reports and data become better interpretable, usable and comparable to information from other sectors.

Further details about the checklist, development process and application scenarios are described in an article that will be submitted soon to a peer-reviewed journal.

6. WP1 Pilots

WP1 pilots had the goal of demonstrating that the resources developed by WP1 (OHEJP Glossary and OH-CRAC) and the supporting standards and tools developed by WP3 are practically applicable and generate the expected added value. Based on the lessons learned from the OH pilot studies, WP1 made the necessary adjustments to improve the different resources. WP1 performed the following pilots (the final reports of each pilot can be found as appendices to this deliverable):

WP1 One Health Pilot (Appendix I)

This pilot has been performed in collaboration with the EJP project “Antibiotic Resistance Dynamics” ([ARDIG](#)⁷) and the “German One Health Initiative” ([GOHI](#)⁸). Both projects thematize OH surveillance of antimicrobial resistance in zoonotic and indicator bacteria. The ARDIG project also covers surveillance on antimicrobial use. The WP1 OH Pilot has specifically tested and improved the OH-CRAC, OHEJP Glossary and Glossaryfication web service. This web service was developed to add value to the OHEJP Glossary by generating automatically glossaries for user provided documents (reports, protocols, manuscripts, etc).

EJP ORION WP1 & WP3 supra-national pilot with EFSA & ECDC (Appendix II)

In addition to the originally planned national WP1 pilot, the ORION WP1 and WP3 agreed to pursue together a pilot to test the uptake-potential of WP1 and WP3 solutions by EFSA and ECDC. Under this pilot we have evaluated the potential benefits and usability of the following tools: OH-CRAC (WP1), OHEJP Glossary (WP1) and the Health Surveillance Ontology (WP3).

7. Lessons learned from WP1 Pilots

The lessons learned from the practical application of the WP1 and WP3 resources tested within the pilots have been summarized under each relevant principle in the OHS Codex:

Communication → OHEJP Glossary/Glossaryfication web service

- The development of the OHEJP Glossary requires a collaborative effort involving actors from all OH sectors, disciplines and countries.

⁶ Iowa State University's Virtual Reality Applications Center (VRAC). RIGOR: Reporting Interface for Guidelines on Research, OH-CRAC. Retrieved from <https://aflex.vrac.iastate.edu/checklist/?t=OH-CRAC>

⁷ <https://onehealth.ejp.eu/structure/jrp2-ardig/>

⁸ https://www.gohi.online/GOHI/EN/Home/Homepage_node.html

- This collaborative work implies a continuous content generation, enrichment and curation to assure the quality and reliability of the resources.
- The adoption of such a tool is also dependent on the availability of a solid and flexible infrastructure that supports the collaborative content generation and the curation process.
- The inclusion of glossaries within OH reports thanks to the Glossaryfication web service can improve communication and collaboration across OH sectors in a long term perspective.

Dissemination → OH-CRAC

- The adoption of the OH-CRAC schema can support a clear and complete way of reporting relevant OH surveillance activities, and facilitate cross-sectorial mapping of surveillance meta-information.
- Despite the extra burden of filling in the OH-CRAC, the provisioning of the completed checklist as an appendix to the surveillance data reports/datasets makes reports and data become better interpretable, usable and comparable to information from other OH sectors.

Data → Health Surveillance Ontology

- The conversion of Excel dataset into RDF formats would generate linkable, context-explicit, future-proof versions of the data made public by EFSA/ECDC. It would also allow automated agents to consume and process these data, empowering knowledge discovery.

Under the “Reflections on the OH perspective” section of Appendix I and Appendix II, further details about the lessons learned within each pilot are provided.

APPENDIX I - ONE HEALTH PILOT REPORT WP1

1. Background

The main aim of WP1 was to develop and test a generic strategy/framework to improve One Health Surveillance (OHS) data collection and interpretation that can be adopted by all One Health (OH) sectors. This strategy/framework is called One Health Surveillance Codex (OHS Codex) and it also aims at improving mutual understanding between the different OH sectors and disciplines. Such improved mutual understanding can be achieved by better cross-sector and multi-disciplinary communication, by supporting cross-domain collaboration and knowledge exchange, as well as by resources supporting cross-sectorial data analysis and reporting.

The WP1 OH Pilot was specifically testing and improving two new resources that are available within the OHS Codex: the OHEJP Glossary and the One Health Consensus Report Annotation Checklist (OH-CRAC). The OHEJP Glossary was created to support the mutual understanding of OHS-related terminology within and between OH sectors. It contains an extensive list of OHS-related terms and definitions which were collected - where available - from stakeholders like EFSA and ECDC and other resources. The OH-CRAC was developed to support harmonized reporting of surveillance metadata in future sector-specific or integrated OH surveillance reports. The OH-CRAC can be used as a generic “checklist” that gives advice on what meta-information should be provided in future sector-specific or integrated OH surveillance reports. It also provides an easy-to-adopt proposal on how this meta-information can be provided in a harmonized way within such reports.

For the WP1 OH pilot, the EJP project “Antibiotic Resistance Dynamics” ([ARDIG⁹](#)) and “German One Health Initiative” ([GOHI¹⁰](#)) were chosen as use cases to validate the WP1 pilot study in AMR and AMU domains. Both projects (ARDIG and GOHI) address OH surveillance of antimicrobial resistance (AMR) in zoonotic and indicator bacteria. The ARDIG project also covers surveillance on antimicrobial use (AMU). The WP1 OH pilot was used to support the operationalization and implementation of the developed resources and then provide crucial feedback for future development and dissemination actions.

Further information regarding the background of the WP1 OH pilot can be found under this link: <https://seafiler.bfr.berlin/f/296e76245aad461e9d6e/?dl=1>.

2. Objectives & expected outcomes

The **overall objective** of the WP1 pilot study was to improve the means of cross-sector, interdisciplinary and inter-institutional OHS collaboration, communication and information sharing. In relation to the specific resources developed within WP1, the pilot study objectives are as follows:

For the **OHEJP Glossary**

- Improve coverage of terms used in AMR & AMU monitoring
- Enhance awareness of OHEJP Glossary in the OHS community
- Qualitative assessment of added value (focusing on specific features of the OHEJP Glossary)

⁹ <https://onehealthejp.eu/structure/jrp2-ardig/>

¹⁰ https://www.gohi.online/GOHI/EN/Home/Homepage_node.html

- Develop, test and evaluate the user-friendliness of a “text-processing” web-service that allows to auto-generate glossaries for user-provided reports on the basis of the OHEJP Glossary

For OH-CRAC

- Evaluate practical applicability of the OH-CRAC for the AMR & AMU domain
- Qualitative assessment of the potential to promote the OH-CRAC adoption after the conclusion of ORION

Expected outcomes

- Improved coverage and quality of AMR and AMU related terms within OHEJP Glossary
- A new, validated web-based “text-processing” service allowing semi-automatic glossary generation for user-provided reports based on the OHEJP Glossary
- Improved mutual understanding of OHS-related terminology across sectors involved in AMR & AMU surveillance
- Validated OH-CRAC Checklist including estimate on uptake potential in future surveillance data reports on AMR and AMU in Germany
- Improved genericity¹¹ and usability¹² of the OHEJP Glossary and OH-CRAC
- Improved use and awareness of the OHEJP Glossary and OH-CRAC in the OHS community

3. Performed activities

The work plan of this pilot was split in four independent activities, three dedicated to the OHEJP Glossary and one focused on the OH-CRAC. The tasks, methods and work plans applied for each of the activities are described below.

OHEJP Glossary related activities

The OHEJP Glossary can be accessed via the following website <https://foodrisklabs.bfr.bund.de/ohejp-glossary/> and is developed and maintained as a collaborative effort of three EJP projects ORION, NOVA and COHESIVE, with support from OH experts of EJP stakeholders. The OHEJP Glossary is hosted on a so-called “Virtual Research Environment” (VRE) that was developed within the AGINFRA+ project (see <http://plus.aginfra.eu>). During the development of the OHEJP Glossary and based on the feedback collected from the pilots, additional customized web applications have been developed in order to support the continuous extension, validation and curation of its content. The links to these dedicated services for Glossary curators and editors are also integrated in the VRE within the AGINFRA+ gateway.

The activities related to the OHEJP Glossary in the WP1 pilot focused on:

Activity 1: Review of OHEJP Glossary based on terms used in resources provided by ARDIG and GOHI

The objective of the first activity was to improve the coverage of AMR and AMU related terms within the OHEJP Glossary. For this purpose, ARDIG and GOHI supported us in the

11 i.e. the additional coverage of AMR and AMU terms in the glossary or the ability to use OH-CRAC to collect and structure metadata related to AMR / AMU monitoring

12 i.e. through extended content of the resources or an improved user-interface

acquisition of resources (e.g. OHS reports) that were used to extract OHS terms used in AMR & AMU monitoring, which have not been included in the OHEJP Glossary yet. For each of the candidate terms extracted from the proposed resources a definition was provided. A method to assess the pre- and post-pilot coverage of terms was also developed. Figure 1 shows the work plan designed for this activity.

Figure 1. Work plan designed for Activity 1.

Activity 2: Adoption and usability testing of OHEJP Glossary

In order to promote the adoption and enhance the awareness of the OHEJP Glossary in the OHS community, a plan to disseminate the OHEJP Glossary was designed. This plan (represented in Figure 2) involved the organization of dissemination events, like webinars, and the participation in congresses, symposiums and conferences where experts and stakeholders from different OH sectors, disciplines and countries are attending. The feedback from these dissemination events was collected via surveys specifically designed to qualitatively assess the following indicators: usefulness, learning curve, performance and scalability, openness and fairness and uptake potential. The results from the evaluation of these surveys/polls was ultimately used to improve the quality of the OHEJP Glossary.

Under this activity, it was also planned to develop a method to track the access rate to the glossary. The OHEJP Glossary uses as a technological backbone the VRE provided by the the AGINFRA+ project, which allows the use of the [Google Analytics](https://analytics.google.com/analytics/web/provision/#/provision) service¹³ to track and report the website traffic.

Figure 2. Work plan designed for Activity 2.

Activity 3: Development and usability testing of a document-specific glossary creation web-service

In order to provide added value to the OHEJP Glossary, a new web-based “text processing” service called **Glossaryfication web service** was developed. This service generates automatically glossaries for user provided documents (reports, papers, etc.) on the basis of

13 <https://analytics.google.com/analytics/web/provision/#/provision>

the OHEJP Glossary (and other online glossaries). The Glossaryfication web service was developed with the open source software KNIME (www.knime.org) using KNIME's Text Processing extension (<https://www.knime.com/knime-text-processing>). As indicated in the work plan (Figure 3), this web service was tested by potential end users in the AMR and AMU domains and the feedback collected from this testing was used to improve its usability and user-friendliness.

Figure 3. Work plan designed for Activity 3.

OH-CRAC related activity

Activity 4: Usability and acceptance testing of OH-CRAC

OH-CRAC was designed to support the creators of future surveillance data (SD) reports in different stages of the surveillance process, and intended to apply to all SD report types, datasets at both national and international level regardless of the data source. In order to evaluate the practical applicability of the OH-CRAC in the AMR and AMU domain, we tested OH-CRAC against a set of reports suggested by ARDIG and GOHI. The results of these OH-CRAC completion exercises were discussed in personal interviews with ARDIG and GOHI representatives and the collected feedback was used to improve the OH-CRAC schema.

Figure 4. Work plan designed for Activity 4.

4. Results

Activity 1: Review of OHEJP Glossary based on terms used in resources provided by ARDIG and GOHI

From the feedback collected in the meetings with ARDIG and GOHI we created a list of the different files and documents that could be used to collect more meaningful terms in the AMR and AMU context. These reports and files were reviewed to find terms that could enrich the OHEJP glossary. The list of AMR and AMU terms with the corresponding definitions is currently under review by ORION WP1 team. Furthermore, ARDIG and GOHI provided feedback regarding the communication issues, differences in terminology and definitions they observe in their fields together with the solutions proposed within the pilot (Table 1).

Table 1. Feedback provided by ARDIG and GOHI regarding the communication issues and specific comments and suggestions related to the OHEJP Glossary together with the solutions that were proposed by WP1 team to solve these issues.

https://knime.bfr.berlin/knime/#/EJP_ORION/Glossary_Maintenance_WF/DeutscheGlossare, Figure 5b).

(a)

German glossaries available

- **BAUA** (Bundesanstalt für Arbeitsschutz und Arbeitsmedizin): Federal Institute for Occupational Safety and Health
- **BfR** (Bundesinstitut für Risikobewertung): German Federal Institute for Risk Assessment
- **BVL** (Bundesamt für Verbraucherschutz und Lebensmittelsicherheit): Federal Office of Consumer Protection and Food Safety
- **EFSA**
- **RKI**: Robert Koch Institute
- **BfArM** (Bundesinstitut für Arzneimittel und Medizinprodukte): Federal Institute for Drugs and Medical Devices
- **Schülke** GmbH - hospital and health care German company

(b)

Figure 5. List of the German glossaries collected (a) and made available under the German glossaries website (b).

Activity 2: Adoption and usability testing of OHEJP Glossary

The adoption of the OHEJP Glossary was tracked using the [Google Analytics](#) service. The Figure 6 shows the results for guest users accessing the catalogue and the access to the catalogue by both guests and registered users.

(a)

Figure 6. Google analytics results from OHEJP Glossary since January to December 2020 for: (a) guest users accessing the catalogue; (b) both guest and known users.

The metrics analyzed by Google analytics in this report are the following:

- *Page views*: the number of times the website has been accessed (including multiple page views by the same visitor) in the chosen period of time
- *Unique Page Views*: indicates the unique number of page views, counting multiple page views by the same visitor in a session as one.
- *Avg. Time on Page*: shows the roughly how much a user spends on the website during a specific time frame.
- *Entrance*: shows the number of users who began their session with this page.
- *Bounce Rate*: shows the percentage of people who left the website after only accessing one page.
- *% Exit*: shows the percentage of which a page was the last one accessed by the visitor before leaving the website.

In total, the glossary received a total of 759 visits, of which 448 correspond to guest users. In 2020, a regular pattern of visits was observed throughout the year with a greater number of visits between April and May.

In order to enhance the awareness in the OHS community, the functionalities and features of the OHEJP Glossary were disseminated and demonstrated in conferences and dedicated webinars:

- Webinar: first version of ORION glossary. 6 November 2018. Recording available here: <https://goo.gl/sUWj2c>.
- ASM Scientific conference 2019 (oral presentation): “The ORION Glossary - An Essential Tool to Support Cross-sectoral and Transdisciplinary Communication in One Health Surveillance”. 21-24 May 2019, Dublin.

- Webinar WP1 OHEJP Glossary. 4 September 2019. Recording available here: <https://svasweden.adobeconnect.com/pm7lzofjjogo/>.
- Symposium „Zoonosen und Lebensmittelsicherheit (oral presentation): ”Das One Health EJP Glossar - eine web-basierte Lösung zur Unterstützung der sektor-übergreifenden Kommunikation im One Health Bereich“. 4-5 November 2019, Berlin.
- ORION KnowledgeHub Webinar. 6 December 2019. Recording available here: <https://svasweden.adobeconnect.com/p90575ar1eht/>.
- ORION Cogwheel workshop. “OHEJP Glossary”. 5 October 2020. Recording available here: <https://svasweden.adobeconnect.com/p1wuf07ym9pu/>.
- 38th meeting of the Scientific Network for Zoonoses monitoring data, EFSA, (oral presentation). “Join Integrative Project ORION EFSA-ECDC supra-national pilot”. 19th – 20th October 2020, online event. Link to presentation: <https://onehealth.ejp.eu/wp-json/pm/v2/projects/88/files/20651/users/1898/download>.
- One Health EJP Continuing Professional Development Module. “The OHEJP Glossary - A Tool to Support Cross-sectoral and Transdisciplinary Communication in One Health Surveillance”. 15-19 February 2021, online workshop. <https://bfr-elearning.de>.
- Throughout the ORION project, all the OHEJP Glossary updates were communicated in the trimonthly web meetings for the whole ORION consortium where stakeholders and interested EJP members participated. The functionality and usability of the OHEJP glossary was also tested and disseminated in the OHEJP ORION WP1 & WP3 supra-national pilot, further details are provided in the corresponding report.

After the webinar held in September 2019, we carried out an online survey covering the following indicators: usefulness, learning curve, performance and scalability, openness and fairness and uptake potential. For each indicator, a set of VRE specific questions were designed in order to qualitatively score the OHEJP Glossary features. The second evaluation of the OHEJP Glossary was performed after the webinar organized in December 2019 following “The Unified Theory on Acceptance and Use of Technology (UTAUT)” proposed by Venkatesh et al. (2003)¹⁴. All the evaluation indicators, survey questions and answers for each webinar have been added as Annexes to this report (Annexes 2 & 3). Based on the answers from these surveys and the general end-user feedback received after the webinars, pilot dedicated meetings and conferences, we conclude that the established OHEJP Glossary is considered relevant for potential end-users and that there is a significant interest in adopting the OHEJP Glossary.

Activity 3: Development and usability testing of document-specific glossary creation web service

The prototypic Glossaryfication web service was deployed on BfR's KNIME Server infrastructure providing an easy-to-use web interface for end-users. The Glossaryfication web service reads in documents provided by the end user via the web portal and, based on text processing technologies, identifies all terms within any user-provided text documents. If there is any matching term in the OHEJP Glossary or any of the other user-selected online glossaries these corresponding definition from the online glossary is provided to the user. The main output is thus a downloadable list of matching glossary terms as well as their

¹⁴ Venkatesh, Viswanath, et al. “User Acceptance of Information Technology: Toward a Unified View.” MIS Quarterly, vol. 27, no. 3, 2003, pp. 425–478. JSTOR, www.jstor.org/stable/30036540.

corresponding definitions and sectorial assignments. A prototype of the Glossaryfication web service can be accessed at the following link: <https://foodrisklabs.bfr.bund.de/ohejp-glossary/>

Within the pilot, ARDIG and GOHI members had the chance to test the Glossaryfication web service and based on the feedback collected we updated this tool by adding the following features:

Improvement of the usability and result view (inclusion of the total number of terms found in the text, limit the inexact matches distance to 2, provision of more precise references to the terms obtained from external glossaries).

Addition of new glossaries relevant for their work. Apart from the OHEJP Glossary, the Glossaryfication service was extended to also include other relevant glossaries. Two distinct services were deployed on the BfR's KNIME Server, the first one containing the [English glossaries](#) (OHEJP, CDC, EFSA and WHO glossaries) and the second one with the [German glossaries](#) identified in the Activity 1 of the pilot (BAUA, BfR, BVL, EFSA, RKI, BfArM and Schülke).

Activity 4: Usability and acceptance testing of OH-CRAC

In the first stage of this activity we reviewed the monitoring and surveillance systems that collect AMR/AMU data in Germany (listed in Table 2) and analyzed the reporting methods applied by each of them. The potential benefits and usability of the OH-CRAC were evaluated by testing OH-CRAC against different surveillance data report types (zoonotic diseases in humans and animals, foodborne outbreaks and antimicrobial resistance). The outcome of these checklist completion exercises can be found under the following link <https://seafiler.bfr.berlin/d/0ff8af0fbfb5421480c4/>. The results of these tests were discussed with the representatives of ARDIG and GOHI and were useful to refine the checklist:

- improving the naming of the checklist items and the comprehensibility of the descriptions
- providing better examples of linked metadata
- identifying missing meta-information or concepts in both OH-CRAC and in the reports

In order to improve the usability of the tool, OH-CRAC was made available as an online resource under the RIGOR platform (<https://aflex.vrac.iastate.edu/checklist/?t=OH-CRAC>) for functional meta-information extraction in reports/documents uploaded as pdf files.

We also organized a dedicated meeting with the German Federal Office of Consumer Protection and Food Safety (BVL) to promote the OH-CRAC idea and assess the options for practical adoption in future SD reports that are created by BVL.

Table 2. List of the monitoring and surveillance systems that collect AMR/AMU data in Germany.

Name	Institution	Type of report
ARS	Robert Koch Institute	Interactive database
ARMIN	Federal state Lower Saxony	Interactive tool
SARI (Surveillance of Antimicrobial Use and Bacterial Resistance in Intensive Care Units)	Institute for Hygiene and Environmental Medicine	They just share some figures and tables but no report, the protocols are also available

MRSA-KISS Referenzdaten MRSA (Methicillin resistenter <i>S. aureus</i>) KISS (Krankenhaus-Infektions-Surveillance-System)	National reference center for surveillance of nosocomial infections	Protocol and results in different files
ICU-KISS and OP-KISS	National reference center for surveillance of nosocomial infections	Protocol and results in different files
PEG Database and Reports	Paul -Ehrlich-Gesellschaft für Chemotherapie	The most recent is from 2013 but has M&M section
BARDA The Bavarian Antibiotic Resistance Database	The Bavarian Antibiotic Resistance Database.	Info displayed on the web very brief results shown in tables
GERMAP report on Antibiotic Consumption and the Spread of Antibiotic Resistance in Human and Veterinary Medicine in Germany	Paul -Ehrlich-Gesellschaft für Chemotherapie Paul Ehrlich Society for Chemotherapy & BVL (Federal Office of Consumer Protection and Food Safety)	GERMAP reports provide a summary of data on the consumption of antimicrobials and the extent of resistances against antimicrobials in human and veterinary medicine. They have an OH approach.
GERMVET National resistance monitoring of animal pathogenic bacteria	BVL (Federal Office of Consumer Protection and Food Safety)	GERMVET collects clinical AMR data in Germany from companion and food producing animals.
ZOMO AMR-testing in the Zoonosis-Monitoring system	BfR, published by BVL (Federal Office of Consumer Protection and Food Safety)	ZOMO presents the data from AMR testing in the German Zoonosis Monitoring System

5. Implementation and impacts

OHEJP Glossary

Based on the feedback received during application of this resource in this pilot, we focused on the development and maintenance of the OHEJP Glossary, which implies the continuous extension, curation and validation of its content. This process was supported by the implementation of new infrastructure, which offers the necessary technical and operational resources to:

Provide an open, user-friendly and searchable infrastructure that complies with the FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable) data principles. ARDIG and GOHI projects representatives valued very positively the benefit of having all these definitions that have been reviewed and curated from experts in different OH sectors in one place.

Search and filter for entries in the glossary. This feature is very useful to reduce misunderstandings as the ones indicated in AMR by ARDIG and GOHI (Table 1), since it highlights the differences and similarities in the interpretation of terms by the different OH sectors, disciplines and stakeholders.

Provide a reference to the source of each definition and a Unique Resource Identifier (URI) for specific referencing of each glossary entry.

Extend, curate and validate the content provided in the OHEJP Glossary. The curation of the OHEJP Glossary is a continuously ongoing process and therefore, a critical step, which is also supported via a dedicated infrastructure. The enrichment of the OHEJP Glossary with AMR-related terms found in the context of this pilot will be easily manageable with the developed infrastructure.

All these functionalities increased the uptake potential and future exploitation of the OHEJP Glossary.

Glossaryfication web service

The Glossaryfication web service provides a solution to enrich future surveillance and research data reports with more comprehensive and unambiguous glossaries. The addition of glossaries to individual documents was considered important to facilitate the coherent interpretation of used terms and help avoid misunderstandings across sectors. Furthermore, it improves the referentiality of terms and definitions from different OH sectors. An additional feature provided by the Glossaryfication web service is the possibility of extending its use to other glossaries from other national or international institutions. This functionality allows the final user to combine different glossaries and customize this glossary creation service.

OH-CRAC

The adoption of the OH-CRAC checklist allows an easier comparison and interpretation of surveillance data reports from different OH sectors as it supports the provisioning of all relevant meta-information. In this pilot, the testing of OH-CRAC helped us to identify missing meta-information or concepts in both the SD reports and in OH-CRAC. This analysis allowed us to cover all relevant meta-information critical for all target sectors and this way support a broad adoption of this framework by all OH-related sectors. To some degree OH-CRAC can therefore be considered as an OH dictionary on surveillance metadata that is useful for “the other” OH sectors.

Regarding the OH-CRAC usability, ARDIG and GOHI highlighted that the completion of the checklist in the report generation process can help authors since OH-CRAC helps to easily identify meta-information missing or meta-information that can be relevant for other sectors. Furthermore, the provisioning of the completed checklist together with the reports would give an added value to their work allowing the readers from other sectors to better interpret the report outcomes.

6. Reflections on the OH perspective

6.1 The OH evaluation matrix: where we are today, what we expect and then – what we achieved.

The OH evaluation matrix is not applicable to this pilot, as this pilot did not aim at improving the level of cross-sectorial integration at any specific step of the surveillance pathway. Instead, the aim was to provide an evaluation (and improvement) of specific tools that can help to improve the communication and information exchange across sectors in the future (see 6.2).

6.2 Lessons learned under each relevant principle in the OHS Codex

- Collaboration

The collaboration and communication between different sectors is the base for OH surveillance and it is still challenging due to differences in terminology and

interpretation of terms in different OH sectors. This frequently leads to misunderstandings and misinterpretations in verbal and written communication. In this sense, the possibility to easily include a detailed glossaries in future surveillance data reports will hopefully be broadly used by the relevant reporting officers. The OHEJP Glossary and the Glossaryfication web service will in this way contribute to better communication, collaboration and (data) comparability between organizations and OHS sectors.

The development of the OHEJP Glossary requires a collaborative effort involving actors from all OH sectors, disciplines and countries. This collaborative work implies a continuous content generation, enrichment and curation to assure the quality and reliability of the resources. Therefore, the adoption of such a tool is also dependent on the availability of a solid and flexible infrastructure that supports the collaborative content generation and the curation process.

- Dissemination

A good dissemination of surveillance findings to stakeholders and surveillance actors is the basis for risk assessment and decision support. The cross-sectorial comparison of surveillance results from sector-specific reports is frequently difficult as reports lack some relevant background meta-information on the surveillance context. These reporting deficiencies reduce the value of sector-specific surveillance reports within the OH community. The adoption of the proposed OH-CRAC schema supports the clear and complete reporting of relevant OH surveillance activities and facilitates a cross-sectorial mapping of surveillance meta-information. Despite the extra burden of filling in the checklist, the provisioning of the completed OH-CRAC checklist as an appendix to the corresponding surveillance data reports or datasets files makes reports and data become better interpretable, usable and comparable to information from other OH sectors.

6.3 SWOT-like considerations for

<u>Process</u>	
Things that worked very well during the study	Positive feedback received for both resources
Things that were difficult or didn't work well during the pilot study	Certain reluctance to adopt new tools when the implementation involves an extra burden
<u>Outcome/product</u>	
Prospects for implementation of the pilot study outcome and further development opportunities	Continuous implementation of new features based on end-users and testing feedback OH-CRAC was presented to the Federal Office of Consumer Protection and Food Safety (BVL) to collect feedback regarding its practical applicability and prospect its potential adoption
Expectations that were not fulfilled and/or barriers for uptake	Risk that necessary funding for long term maintenance is not guaranteed

7. Annex 1: List of publications, presentations

- Webinar: first version of ORION glossary. 6 November 2018. Recording available here: <https://goo.gl/sUWj2c>.
- ASM Scientific conference 2019 (Presentation): “The ORION Glossary - An Essential Tool to Support Cross-sectoral and Transdisciplinary Communication in One Health Surveillance”. 21-24 May 2019, Dublin.
- Webinar WP1 OHEJP Glossary. 4 September 2019. Recording available here: <https://svasweden.adobeconnect.com/pm7lzofjogo/>.
- Symposium „Zoonosen und Lebensmittelsicherheit (oral presentation): “Das One Health EJP Glossar - eine web-basierte Lösung zur Unterstützung der sektor-übergreifenden Kommunikation im „One Health“ Bereich“. 4-5 November 2019, Berlin.
- ORION KnowledgeHub Webinar. 6 December 2019. Recording available here: <https://svasweden.adobeconnect.com/p90575ar1eht/>.
- ASM Scientific conference 2020 (oral presentation): “One Health Consensus Report Annotation Checklist (OH-CRAC): a generic checklist to support harmonization of surveillance data reports”. 27-29 May 2020, online event.
- ASM Scientific conference 2020 (Poster presentation): “Text mining technology as added-value infrastructure to the One Health EJP Glossary”. 27-29 May 2020, online event.
- BfR internal colloquium (oral presentation): “Der "Glossaryfication" Webdienst - automatisierte Glossarerstellung zur Unterstützung des One Health Ansatzes“. 20 October 2020, Berlin.
- ORION Cogwheel workshop. 5 October 2020. Recording available here: <https://svasweden.adobeconnect.com/p1wuf07ym9pu/>
- 38th meeting of the Scientific Network for Zoonoses monitoring data, EFSA, (oral presentation). 19th – 20th October 2020. “Join Integrative Project ORION EFSA-ECDC supra-national pilot”, online event. Link to presentation: <https://onehealth.ejp.eu/wp-json/pm/v2/projects/88/files/20651/users/1898/download>.
- World One Health Congress (poster presentation): “One Health Consensus Report Annotation Checklist (OH-CRAC): a framework for harmonization of surveillance data reports”. 30th October-3rd November 2020, online event.
- World One Health Congress (poster presentation): “The Glossaryfication web service: an automated glossary creation tool to support the One Health community”. 30th October-3rd November 2020, online event.
- One Health EJP Continuing Professional Development Module 2021. “The OHEJP Glossary - A Tool to Support Cross-sectoral and Transdisciplinary Communication in One Health Surveillance”. 15-19 February 2021, online workshop. <https://bfr-elearning.de>.
- One Health EJP Continuing Professional Development Module 2021. “Data structuring and harmonization practices examples (OH-CRAC)”. 15-19 February 2021, online workshop. <https://bfr-elearning.de>.

This meeting is part of the European Joint Programme One Health EJP.
This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020
research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 773830.

- One Health EJP Continuing Professional Development Module 2021. “The Glossaryfication web service: an automated glossary creation tool to support the One Health community”. 15-19 February 2021, online workshop. <https://bfr-elearning.de>.
- ORION full consortium open day. “WP1 outcomes (OHEJP Glossary, Glossaryfication web service and OH-CRAC) & WP1 OH pilot results”. 9 March 2021, online meeting. Recording available here: <https://seafle.bfr.berlin/f/994b91c5261d4986a5a2/>.

8. Annex 2: Survey results - OHEJP Glossary webinar

4th September 2019 from 10:00 to 11:00 AM via

https://svasweden.adobeconnect.com/ejp_orion/

Tutors:

Matthias Filter, Tasja Buschhardt & Taras Günther

Agenda:

1. Welcome, Introduction of Speakers, Agenda
2. Introduction to EJP & AGINFRA+ Projects
3. OHEJP Glossary - Background
4. OHEJP Glossary - Technical Concept & Live Demo
5. OHEJP Glossary - Summary & Future Perspectives
6. Q&A & Feedback

Table 8.1: Evaluation metrics used in the second pilot VRE version for VRE-based OHEJP Glossary use case and graphical representation of the answers provided.

Indicators	Evaluation questions	Assessment method	Answers
1. Usefulness	How do you assess the usefulness of the VRE-based OHEJP Glossary with regard to the following three aspects: - Content?	Qualitative scoring <i>Not useful</i> <i>OK</i> <i>Very useful</i> <i>Other</i>	100,0% ● Very useful
	How do you assess the usefulness of the pilot VRE with regard to the following aspects: - Functionality (eg. sorting, searching content)?	Qualitative scoring <i>Not useful</i> <i>OK</i> <i>Very useful</i> <i>Other</i>	80,0% 20,0% ● Very useful ● OK

	<p>How do you assess the usefulness of the pilot VRE with regard to the following aspects:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Collaboration and communication? 	<p>Qualitative scoring</p> <p><i>Not useful</i> <i>OK</i> <i>Very useful</i> <i>Other</i></p>	<p>● Very useful ● Not useful</p>
	<p>Do you think that the VRE-based OHEJP Glossary can help to perform your work “in the cloud” and support co-development by remote researcher and research teams?</p>	<p>Qualitative scoring</p> <p><i>No</i> <i>Maybe</i> <i>Yes</i> <i>Other</i></p>	<p>● Yes ● Maybe</p>
	<p>Which features presented in the VRE-based OHEJP Glossary are considered as relevant for your research?</p>	<p>Qualitative scoring</p> <p><i>Free text</i></p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Search and filter function - unique ID for terms, search for terms, tagging of terms - Term definitions, references and URL for referencing - Different terms for different sectors
<p>2. Learning curve</p>	<p>How do you estimate the effort to learn how to access, search and filter content in the VRE-based OHEJP Glossary?</p>	<p>Qualitative scoring</p> <p><i>Short</i> <i>Medium</i> <i>Long</i> <i>Very long</i> <i>Other</i></p>	<p>● Short ● Medium</p>
	<p>How do you estimate the effort to use the VRE-based OHEJP Glossary for your own research, e.g. to search, compare or reference definitions with the VRE-based OHEJP Glossary?</p>	<p>Qualitative scoring</p> <p><i>Low</i> <i>Medium</i> <i>High</i> <i>Other</i></p>	<p>● Low ● High</p>

3. Performance, scalability	How do you rate the performance of the VRE-based OHEJP Glossary compared to the platform(s) you are used to work with?	Qualitative scoring <i>Poor</i> <i>OK</i> <i>Good</i> <i>Very good</i>	<p>60,0% 40,0%</p> <p>● Very good ● Good</p>
	How do you rate the scalability of the VRE-based OHEJP Glossary?	Qualitative scoring <i>Poor</i> <i>OK</i> <i>Good</i> <i>Very good</i>	<p>40,0% 60,0%</p> <p>● Very good ● Good</p>
4. Openness and FAIRness	How open do you think the OHEJP Glossary and its tools are from the following three perspectives: - Ease of finding and accessing definitions and references?	Qualitative scoring <i>Poor</i> <i>OK</i> <i>Good</i> <i>Very good</i>	<p>60,0% 40,0%</p> <p>● Very good ● Good</p>
	How open do you think the pilot and its tools are from the following perspectives? - Ease of comparing terms and definitions between different sectors?	Qualitative scoring <i>Poor</i> <i>OK</i> <i>Good</i> <i>Very good</i>	<p>40,0% 40,0% 20,0%</p> <p>● Very good ● Good ● OK</p>
	How open do you think the pilot and its tools are from the following perspectives: - Ease of referencing and sharing terms?	Qualitative scoring <i>Poor</i> <i>OK</i> <i>Good</i> <i>Very good</i>	<p>60,0% 40,0%</p> <p>● Very good ● Good</p>

5. Uptake potential	What is the likelihood that you would use a system as the one demonstrated in the VRE-based OHEJP Glossary in the future for your work?	Qualitative scoring <i>Will not use</i> <i>May use</i> <i>Will use</i> <i>Other</i>	<table border="1"><thead><tr><th>Category</th><th>Percentage</th></tr></thead><tbody><tr><td>Will use</td><td>80,0%</td></tr><tr><td>May use</td><td>20,0%</td></tr></tbody></table>	Category	Percentage	Will use	80,0%	May use	20,0%
Category	Percentage								
Will use	80,0%								
May use	20,0%								

9. Annex 3: Survey results - ORIONKnowledgeHub webinar

6th December 2019 from 1:00 to 4:00 PM via https://svasweden.adobeconnect.com/ejp_orion/

Webinar agenda:

- 1:00 – 1:15 PM Welcome, Agenda, Introduction to the ORION project (ORION Coordination)
- 1:15 – 1:45 PM The One Health Surveillance (OHS) Codex Framework and its components (WP1)
- 1:45 – 2:15 PM The OHS Knowledgebase (WP2-Epi)
- 2:15 – 2:45 PM The OHS NGS Handbook (WP2-NGS)
- 2:45 – 3:15 PM The OH Integration Idea Catalogue (WP2-Int)
- 3:15 – 3:45 PM The OHS Harmonization Tools (WP3)
- 3:45 – 4:00 PM Question & Answers (ORION Coordination)

Summary:

The OHEJP Glossary was presented as one of the new components of the OHS Codex that was presented by WP1.

Table 9.1: Results of the validation of the final pilot VRE version using the UTAUT: The Unified Theory on Acceptance and Use of Technology” (Venkatesh et al., 2003) approach for ORION use case.

Indicator of the pilot VRE	Question	Rating (No. answers per rating option)					Mean
		1	2	3	4	5	
Performance expectancy	1. I would find the OHEJP Glossary useful in my job.	0	0	1	2	3	3.50
	2. Using the OHEJP Glossary would enable me to accomplish tasks more quickly.	0	0	2	3	1	2.67
	3. Using the OHEJP Glossary would increase my productivity.	0	0	2	3	1	2.67
	4. If I used the OHEJP Glossary, I would increase my chances of getting a better position or salary.	2	0	4	0	0	3.33
Effort expectancy	5. My interaction with the OHEJP Glossary would be clear and understandable.	0	0	2	3	1	2.67
	6. It would be easy for me to become skillful at using the OHEJP Glossary.	1	0	1	0	4	4.33
	7. I would find the OHEJP Glossary easy to use.	0	0	0	1	5	4.33
	8. Learning to operate the OHEJP Glossary would be easy for me.	0	0	0	2	4	3.67
Attitude toward using technology	9. Using the OHEJP Glossary is a good idea.	0	0	0	2	4	3.67
	10. The OHEJP Glossary makes work more interesting.	0	0	3	1	2	3.83
	11. Working with the OHEJP Glossary is fun.	0	0	3	1	2	3.83
	12. I would like working with the OHEJP Glossary.	0	0	2	1	3	4.00
Social influence	13. People who influence my behavior would think that I should use the OHEJP Glossary.	0	0	3	1	2	3.83
	14. People who are important to me would think that I should use the OHEJP Glossary.	0	0	2	2	2	3.33

	15. The senior management of my organisation would be supportive of using the OHEJP Glossary.	0	0	0	2	4	3.67
	16. In general, my organization would support the use of the OHEJP Glossary.	0	0	0	1	5	4.33
Facilitating conditions	17. I have the resources necessary to adopt and use the OHEJP Glossary.	0	0	0	1	5	4.33
	18. I have the knowledge necessary to adopt and use the OHEJP Glossary.	0	0	0	1	5	4.33
	19. The OHEJP Glossary does not seem compatible with other systems I use.	4	1	1	0	0	2.50
	20. In my organisation, a specific person (or group) would be available to assist me with system difficulties.	0	2	2	1	1	3.33
Self-efficacy	21. I could complete a job or task using the OHEJP Glossary if there was no one around to tell me what to do as I go.	0	0	1	1	4	4.17
	22. I could complete a job or task using the OHEJP Glossary if I could call someone for help if I got stuck.	0	0	0	2	4	3.67
	23. I could complete a job or task using the OHEJP Glossary if I had a lot of time to complete the job for which the software was provided.	0	0	2	0	4	4.67
	24. I could complete a job or task using the OHEJP Glossary if I had in my organisation facility for assistance.	0	1	1	0	4	4.50
Anxiety	25. I feel apprehensive about using the OHEJP Glossary.	4	1	0	0	1	2.67
	26. It scares me to think that I could lose a lot of information using the OHEJP Glossary by hitting the wrong key.	4	0	2	0	0	2.67
	27. I hesitate to use the OHEJP Glossary for fear of making mistakes I cannot correct.	4	2	0	0	0	2.33
	28. The OHEJP Glossary looks somewhat intimidating to me.	4	2	0	0	0	2.33
Behavioral intention to use the system	29. I intend to use the OHEJP Glossary in the next 12 months.	0	0	1	1	4	4.17
	30. I predict I would use the OHEJP Glossary in the next 12 months.	0	0	1	1	4	4.17
	31. I plan to use the OHEJP Glossary in the next 12 months.	0	0	1	1	4	4.17
Gender	Female	4					
	Male	2					
	Prefer not to say	0					
Average age	39.5 years old						

APPENDIX II - OHEJP ORION WP1&WP3 SUPRA-NATIONAL PILOT REPORT

Executive summary

Under the Joint Integrative Project (JIP) “One health surveillance Initiative on harmonization of data collection and interpretation” (ORION) (<https://onehealthjep.eu/jip-orion/>), the ORION WP1 & WP3 supra-national pilot aimed to test the functionality and usability of the ORION solutions developed so far with the support of international stakeholders such as EFSA (European Food Safety Authority) and ECDC (European Centre for Disease Prevention and Control).

Selected solutions developed by the ORION project were tested within the supra-national, namely: i) the OHEJP Glossary & Glossaryfication web service, ii) the One Health Consensus Report Annotation Checklist (OH-CRAC) and iii) the Health Surveillance Ontology (HSO).

Under work package (WP) 1 of ORION project, the OHEJP Glossary (<https://onehealthjep.eu/jip-orion/>) was created to facilitate the mutual understanding of One Health Surveillance (OHS) related terminology. It aims to improve communication and collaboration among One Health (OH) sectors by providing an online resource of relevant OH terms and their definitions. Within the supra-national pilot, the Glossaryfication web service was generated as added value infrastructure to the OHEJP Glossary. The Glossaryfication web service is an easy-to-use infrastructure that allows the user to automatically create glossaries during reports writing and its aim is to provide a solution to enrich future OHS documents with more comprehensive and unambiguous glossaries.

Also, under the WP1, the OH-CRAC was produced as general checklist to support harmonization of OHS reports. The OH-CRAC gives recommendations on what meta-information should be provided and how to structure it within future surveillance data reports. The OH-CRAC was extensively validated, improved and applied within the supra-national pilot. The completion of OH-CRAC examples was carried out against *Salmonella* and *Campylobacter* pathogens for several OH reports (e.g. the European Union OH 2018 Zoonoses Report). Another use of the OH-CRAC that emerged was its applicability as meta-information sheet to enrich EFSA dataset published on the EFSA Knowledge Junction on Zenodo with all their relevant meta-information to help the final user to understand the OH dataset. Further, this resource has been made available as web-based interactive annotating tool (<https://aflex.vrac.iastate.edu/checklist/?t=OH-CRAC>) for functional meta-information extraction in reports/documents uploaded as pdf files.

Finally, WP3 of the ORION project focused on the development of technical infrastructure to support data interoperability among health surveillance agencies. The WP3 solutions relevant

This meeting is part of the European Joint Programme One Health EJP.
This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020
research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 773830.

for the supra-national pilot are the HSO and a software tool to create Linked-Open-Data (LOD) from an Excel template (Excel2RDF). Within the supra-national pilot, a new web service to facilitate the semi-automatic mapping of concepts from the EFSA's catalogues into the HSO was developed. This web service helps to create an easy maintainable link between the constantly evolving EFSA catalogues and the HSO that can be exploited by future semantic search technologies and services. Additionally, the possible generation of LOD of the EFSA and ECDC datasets via the HSO for user-friendly visualization tool was initiated.

1. Background

This report refers to one of the One-Health (OH) pilot initiatives carried out by the Joint Integrative Project ORION, part of the OH European Joint Programme (OHEJP). The activities of this, which will be from here on referred to as “the supra-national pilot”, were designed as a joint activity between ORION’s work packages WP1 and WP3, and the European agencies EFSA and ECDC. A description of the pilot design is available at: <https://data.d4science.net/R3wJ> or

https://onehealth.ejp.eu/?get_group_doc=103/1611778897-ORION_WP1-3_PilotStudyDescription_EFSA-ECDC.docx

2. Objectives and expected outcomes

The objectives, expected outcomes and the work plan of the supra-national pilot are provided at these following links:

- Supra-national pilot description: <https://data.d4science.net/R3wJ>;
- Supra-national pilot work plan: <https://drive.google.com/file/d/1a2L2bR7M6tCWt7Dm9dwf-5Z7qv7Kxusl/view?usp=sharing>.

3. Performed activities

The supra-national pilot started in January 2020 (M25). The overall aim was to evaluate the applicability of selected ORION solutions developed by WP1 and WP3 to improve the process of generating information valuable in an OH context by EFSA and ECDC. An on-site visit to EFSA was carried out in the beginning of the supra-national pilot (25th – 27th February 2020). During this visit the detailed work plan, linked above, was created. Tasks were designed around the testing and evaluation of the main ORION solutions: i) OHEJP Glossary, ii) One Health Consensus Report Annotation Checklist and the iii) Health Surveillance Ontology.

3.1. The OHEJP Glossary and the Glossaryfication web service

The OHEJP Glossary web-portal (<https://aginfra.d4science.org/web/orionknowledgehub/catalogue>), created under ORION’s WP1, provides an online resource of relevant OH terms and definitions from the public health, animal health and food safety sectors. For each of the terms, a unique identifier, reference to the original publication, and OH-related meta-information such as assignment to the specific sector are provided. Within the supra-national pilot, a new technical infrastructure named “Glossaryfication web service” was implemented, adding value to the OHEJP glossary resource. The Glossaryfication web service is a user-friendly web-based tool that allows end-users to automatically create glossaries for their own documents based on the OHEJP

Glossary (and other glossaries available online). This document-specific glossary creation service was developed with the open source software KNIME (<https://www.knime.com/>) and uses KNIME's Text Processing extension (<https://hub.knime.com/knime/extensions/org.knime.features.ext.textprocessing/latest>). The Glossaryfication KNIME workflow is deployed on BfR's KNIME Server infrastructure. The Glossaryfication KNIME workflow reads in documents provided by the end user via the web interface and applies natural language processing, text mining and information retrieval methods to identify matching terms in the available glossaries. The web service also automatically retrieves updates from the OHEJP Glossary by machine-to-machine communication. Additionally, the Glossaryfication web service allows the use of other glossaries as a source. Besides the OHEJP Glossary, other glossaries from national and international institutions (CDC, EFSA, WHO etc.) can be used. However, the OHEJP Glossary is the only One Health curated glossary. A prototype of the Glossaryfication web service is available and can be accessed at the following link: https://knime.bfr.berlin/knime/#/EJP_ORION/Text%20Processing%20Technology/Glossaryfication-Service&single&run using the login credential - Username: ORION, Password: OneHealth. A similar workflow has been created for German glossaries that can be accessed via the following link: https://knime.bfr.berlin/knime/#/EJP_ORION/Text%20Processing%20Technology/Glossaryfication-ServiceGerman&single&run.

Once the user has been logged into any of the Glossaryfication web services, a brief description of the tool is provided (**Figure 1**).

Figure 1. Screenshot of the Glossaryfication web service. Through the service, the end-users can upload a specific file (yellow box B) and select the given glossary(ies) options (yellow box A).

Users can upload any document (PDF, Word, Excel files format) and choose one or all glossaries. The service will automatically search within the user-provided text document for terms that are contained in the selected glossary(ies). The user will receive a downloadable list of matching glossary terms with their corresponding definitions, which can be added to the user's document (see section 4. Results).

3.2. The **One Health Consensus Report Annotation Checklist**

The One Health Consensus Report Annotation Checklist (OH-CRAC) (<https://oh-surveillance-codex.readthedocs.io/en/latest/5-the-dissemination-principle.html>) was previously produced under ORION's WP1 as general checklist to support harmonization of OH surveillance (OHS) reports. The OH-CRAC gives recommendations on what meta-information should be provided and how to structure it within future surveillance data reports. The usability of OH-CRAC was evaluated within the supra-national pilot. The OH-CRAC checklist was presented and discussed along with the main stakeholders in order to identify missing meta-information or concepts. The OH-CRAC schema was tested against different OH surveillance reports, specifically for zoonotic diseases in humans and animals (*Salmonella* and *Campylobacter*), foodborne outbreaks and antimicrobial resistance. Examples of the completion of OH-CRAC can be found at the following link: <https://onehealth.ejp.eu/wp-json/pm/v2/projects/88/files/22434/users/1898/download>. Each tab, represents a hazard and sector within these reports. A comparison between hazards and sectors is also provided.

Another use of the OH-CRAC that emerged was its applicability as a meta-information sheet to enrich EFSA's datasets published on the EFSA Knowledge Junction on Zenodo, helping the final user to understand an OH dataset. For instance, the tables complementing the European Union One Health 2018 Zoonoses Report are provided as Excel files in Zenodo. These Excel files display no details about how surveillance was conducted, but this information is already publicly available in the main report. With the OH-CRAC, the idea is that the information available in text format in the main report could be structured following the OH-CRAC checklist and made available at the same location as the data, i.e. inside the same Excel file as the data. One possible way to do that is adding an extra OH-CRAC spreadsheet to the Excel files containing the shared data. The meta-information contained in the checklist would be important to capture the context of data collection, aiding the correct use and interpretation of the data in the Zenodo Excel files.

3.3. The Health Surveillance Ontology

The WP3 of the ORION project focused on the development of technical infrastructure to support data interoperability among health surveillance agencies. The WP3 solutions relevant for the supra-national pilot were the Health Surveillance Ontology (HSO) (<http://datadrivensurveillance.org/health-surveillance-ontology-hso/>), and a software tool to create Linked Open Data (LOD) from an Excel template (Excel2RDF).

The HSO aims to support in the future all metadata used within the Standard Sample Description (SSD) catalogues used for surveillance data reporting from European Member States (MS) to EFSA. Within the supra-national pilot we created a KNIME workflow that supports the incorporation of SSD catalogue items as instances of particular concepts in HSO. This workflow (https://knime.bfr.berlin/knime/#/EJP_ORION/OH-LOD%20Toolbox/HSO_Toolbox/EFSA_Catalogue_HSO&single&run) is useful for the aim to grow and sustain the HSO ontology.

A separate workflow to annotate data using terms provided in HSO was also created (https://knime.bfr.berlin/knime/#/EJP_ORION/OH-LOD%20Toolbox/LOD_Converter/EXCEL_to_RDF&single&run). In this workflow, surveillance data available in Excel format can be converted by using HSO into the Resource Description Framework (RDF) format, which is a standard data model used to allow data interchange on the web. The resulting RDF dataset is an example of semantically explicit and machine-readable surveillance data. Semantic annotation of surveillance data is promoted in ORION as a means to achieve, among other benefits, the ability to link disparate sources of data (creating linked-data).

A third workflow (https://knime.bfr.berlin/knime/#/EJP_ORION/OH-LOD%20Toolbox/LOD_Processing/Linked_Data_example&single&run) was built to “consume” linked data, demonstrating the ability to connect linked-data with other semantic explicit data, such as Wikidata (the machine-readable version of Wikipedia) and open research data repositories. This workflow is able to join RDF datasets and produce user-friendly data visualization outputs. More details about the use of ORION tools to provide interoperability, and how the workflows mentioned here contribute to data FAIRness can be found in the One-Health Surveillance Codex principle dedicated to data issues: <https://oh-surveillance-codex.readthedocs.io/en/latest/4-the-data-principle.html>.

A prototype of the HSO web services is available at the following link: https://knime.bfr.berlin/knime/#/EJP_ORION/HS_Ontology_Workflows using the login credential - Username: ORION, Password: OneHealth.

These workflows are still under implementation, and as the work proceed they will be updated into the BfR's KNIME Server infrastructure so they can be used via web browser.

4. Results

4.1. The Glossaryfication web service

The Glossaryfication web service produces a tag cloud and a table of terms with all available definitions (**Figure 2**). Through an interactive user interface the users can select those terms and corresponding definitions that match the intended meaning within the user provided text document. A list of terms and definitions, along with their sectoral classification, references and their abundance in the provided text document (TF abs) is generated (**Figure 2**). The created table of terms can then easily be downloaded and added to the user's document as a document specific glossary.

Figure 2. Schematic representation of the Glossaryfication web service. Users can upload any kind of text document and successively, matches between the provided text and the OHEJP Glossary (or other selected glossaries) are found. The service provides a tag cloud and a table with exact-, inexact- and non-matching terms which can be download using different options.

4.2. The One Health Consensus Report Annotation Checklist

The OH-CRAC was applied within the supra-national pilot and the validation exercises were useful to improve the naming of the checklist items and the phrasing of the descriptions, to provide more meaningful meta-information examples and to add more subcategories where necessary. Also, in order to facilitate the completion of OH-CRAC, the checklist has been

made available as web-based interactive annotating tool under the RIGOR platform <https://aflex.vrac.iastate.edu/checklist/?t=OH-CRAC> for functional meta-information extraction in reports/documents uploaded as pdf files.

4.3. The Health Surveillance Ontology

The web service created for growing the ontology allows HSO curators to select a concept in the ontology, and then select an SSD catalogue to populate the concept with instances. For example, the HSO concept “Food vehicle” was populated with all instances of the SSD catalogue “ZOO_CAT_FOODVH”. This web service facilitate the semi-automatic mapping of concepts from the SSD catalogues into the HSO developed in WP3. This web service will also help to create a link between the SSD catalogues and the HSO, both meant to continue evolving as knowledge evolves. This link that can be exploited by future semantic search technologies and services that build on LOD. Additionally, the KNIME workflow to produce RDF file format from Excel files can facilitate the generation of LOD for legacy or new datasets open up new opportunities for providing transparent and interoperable data by EFSA and ECDC.

5. Implementation and impacts

5.1. The Glossaryfication web service

Glossaries generated by the glossaryfication web service can be easily included in surveillance reports to support the OH paradigm as it creates awareness of the differences in the interpretation of terms within different OH sectors. The OHEJP Glossaryfication web service provides a solution to enrich future surveillance and research data reports with more comprehensive and unambiguous glossaries.

Furthermore, it improves the referentiality of terms and definitions from different OH sectors. Finally, the possibility to use the glossaries available on EFSA and ECDC's website (and from other national or international institutions) allows now any end user to synchronize the wording in future documents and reports to those definitions given by EFSA and ECDC. It could also be used by EFSA and ECDC themselves to check if the meaning of terms in a given new document corresponds to the “official” definition of their own organization. In cases where this is not the case, a document specific glossary might be even of bigger relevance.

5.2. The One Health Consensus Report Annotation Checklist

The OH-CRAC checklist can also provide a way to improve the generation of future surveillance reports in the OH-context. Indeed, the completeness and transparency of surveillance reports can be improved by the adoption of OH-CRAC schema with a clear and complete reporting of relevant surveillance activities, that to some extent also supports the cross-sectorial mapping of surveillance meta-information. The use of the OH-CRAC checklist during the creation of surveillance report can highlighting missing meta-information which may be relevant for other sectors. Also, the inclusion of the completed checklist along with the surveillance or research data reports would allow the final reader to better interpret the final results of the reports. From the practical application of OH-CRAC on existing EFSA reports it could be concluded, that filled OH-CRAC checklists could easily be attached as Annexes to future surveillance data reports and also be used to link this meta-information to actual data files.

5.3. The Health Surveillance Ontology

The KNIME workflows created under the supra-national pilot for the HSO can facilitate the i) reusing of knowledge from existing terminologies used in OHS into machine readable models; and ii) creation of LOD versions of the data published by EFSA/ECDC. With this the pilot accomplished the objective to illustrate the potential of the linked-data paradigm for the long term future.

6. Reflections on the OH perspective

6.1. Lessons learned under each relevant principle in the OHS Codex

- Collaboration

The inclusion of glossaries within OH reports thanks to the Glossaryfication web service can improve communication and collaboration across OH sectors in a long term perspective.

- Data

The conversion of Excel dataset into RDF formats would generate linkable, context-explicit, future-proof versions of the data made public by EFSA/ECDC. It would also allow automated agents to consume and process these data, empowering knowledge discovery.

- Dissemination

The adoption of the OH-CRAC schema can support a clear and complete way of reporting relevant OH surveillance activities, and facilitate cross-sectorial mapping of surveillance meta-information.

6.2. SWOT-like considerations for

<u>Process</u>	<u>Max 2-3 points in each</u>
Things that worked very well during the study	Positive response from the stakeholder involved and willing to study the applicability of the resources;
Things that were difficult or didn't work well during the pilot study	Interpretation of datasets; constraints to adopt the new prototypic solutions into a "productive" procedure.
<u>Outcome/product</u>	
Prospects for implementation of the pilot study outcome and further development opportunities	We keep implementing the glossaryfication web services and also, the conversion of Excel data files into RDF format for LOD.
Expectations that were not fulfilled and/or barriers for uptake	

7. Annex: List of presentations

1. Scaccia, N., Günther, T., Buschhardt, T., Valentin, L., Filter, M. *The "Glossaryfication" web service: an automated glossary creation tool to support the One Health community.* The 6th World One Health Congress, 30th October – 3rd November 2020, online event.
Poster presentation, link:
<https://onehealthejp.eu/wp-json/pm/v2/projects/88/files/20648/users/1898/download>
2. Scaccia, N., Lopez de Abechucó, E., Günther, T., Dórea, F., Filter, M. *Join Integrative Project ORION EFSA-ECDC supra-national pilot.* 38th meeting of the Scientific Network for Zoonoses monitoring data, 19th – 20th October 2020, online event.
Oral presentation, link:
<https://onehealthejp.eu/wp-json/pm/v2/projects/88/files/20651/users/1898/download>
3. Scaccia, N., Günther, T., Buschhardt, T., Valentin, L., Filter, M. *Text mining technology as added value infrastructure to the One Health EJP Glossary.* One Health EJP Annual Scientific Meeting (ASM), 27th – 29th May 2020, online event.
Poster presentation, link:
<https://onehealthejp.eu/wp-json/pm/v2/projects/88/files/21054/users/1898/download>